

REASONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ATHEISM IN MODERN ERA

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ABSTRACT

God created this world and taught people morals, through prophets. Initially, this society was based on monotheism, but later man divided the doctrine of monotheism. But even in this division, the concept of God remained in some form. Believers of all the religions believe that their God is the God of all other human beings. While there was a group of them who only saw and believed in the rational scientific level and did not believe in the concept of God. Today's world is divided into two ideologies, the first group is religious while the second group belongs to atheism.

In the early days, this group was suppressed by the group of religious people, but in today's era, The group of atheists come out openly and opposing the religion, Therefore, this group is attacking on religion by way of various questions. Based on these questions, it is spreading its ideas.

Key words: Atheism, Atheist, God, Religion, Ethics, Education, Blind Imitation, Economic, Communism, Capitalism, Secularism.

Introduction to Atheism:

The literal meaning of Atheism in the Arabic language is to deviate or deviate from the path. Al-Haad is called Atheism in English. Which in Urdu language means Ladinity, Ignorance. The followers of Al-Haad are called Al-Muhid, Duhrey, Materialist Atheists.

Atheist means one who deviates from the path of truth, immoral, irreligious.

The word Atheism has two meaning first is Lahad (grave) and Second is Lahad (to be ungodly, to turn away, to deviate)

Accoding to Lisan ul Arab

"الشقالذى يكون فى جانب القبر موضع الميت"

"In a grave, there is a place to keep the dead."¹

Atheism: to deviate from the straight path, to deviate from the true religion, to become an atheist.²

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Atheist: One who not walks on the straight path, transgressor, infidel, unbeliever, unbeliever, milch.⁴

The theory or belief that God does not exist.⁵

Atheism refers to the absolute denial of an omnipotent being, whether it is believed to be a single entity or multiple gods. People who hold this view are called Atheists.⁶

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Meaning of Atheism:

Atheism is the denial of God or the gods and that is opposite of theism.⁷

Atheism is the denial of God or gods and is opposed to theism.

The word atheism is generally spoken in the sense of atheism and disbelief in God, a person's denial of any one of the three beliefs of God, Prophethood, Prophethood and the Hereafter is called atheism.⁸

In the Holy Qur'an, in Surah Al-Faslat, Allah says:

إِنَّ الَّذِينَ يُلْحِدُونَ فِي آيَاتِنَا لَا يَخْفَوْنَ عَلَيْنَا أَفَمَنْ يَلْقَى فِي النَّارِ خَيْرًا مِمَّنْ مَنَعَتْ رَأْمَنِيَاتِ ۚ
أَمْ نَأْيُومَ الْقِيَامَةِ ۚ أَعْمَلُوا مَا شِئْتُمْ إِنَّهُ بِمَا تَعْمَلُونَ بَصِيرٌ ۙ 9

"Indeed, those who add to Our verses are not hidden from Us, so is that which is thrown away better or that which will come on the Day of Resurrection with peace and security (that is better), do what you will. He is watching what you do."

Commentary on the above verse is written by Pir Muhammad Karam Shah Al-Azhari in Zia-ul-Quran. An unbeliever is a person who turns away from the truth and mixes in it something that is not in it.¹⁰

Atheism is to deny the existence of Allah, as is the religion of the new and old materialists of the world or the followers of historical materialism.

Atheism generally refers to the denial of God, and dualism is a scholarly debate and movement based on its intellectual formulations and details. In today's world, atheism has become entrenched in the individual and dualism is a major movement. Atheism and dualism is no longer an academic or intellectual issue, but it has become a social and cultural situation that has everywhere. It has also taken the form of a movement. Now the extremism is using "movement" means for its spread and defense and has the huge forces of political power and capital at its back.

Atheism is a term used in Islamic disciplines to refer to infidels (disbelievers in God).

Beliefs: Atheists believe that the world was not created by God, but came into existence by itself or was already there and will always exist in various forms. Atheists only believe in things that have no rational or scientific proof. Almost all atheists have flexible views, so if a theory is proven wrong or can be modified, they are willing to change it over time, and like religious people, whether it is wrong or wrong. They are not convinced to stick to what they believe, besides, they believe in science and worldly sciences, they are very against religious extremism and want the freedom to live as they wish for everyone.¹¹

A History of Atheism

From time immemorial, some people have believed in some form of atheism, but in this case the denial of God's existence has rarely been accepted. Religions include Buddhism, Jainism, and a few philosophers who have believed in God. Denied the existence of. From the historical study, it is known that atheism has never gained strength, the believers of religions have always prevailed in the world. Atheism has developed only in the present age when many nations of the world adopted it. Started adopting.

Size and Projected Growth of Major Religious Groups¹²

Projected Population Growth of Major Religions (2010-2050)

	۲۰۱۰ POPULATION	% OF WORLD POPULATION IN 2010	PROJECTED 2050 POPULATION	% OF WORLD POPULATION IN 2050	POPULATION GROTH 2010- 2050
Christians	2,168,330,000	31.4%	2,918,070,000	31.4%	749,740,000
Muslims	1,599,700,000	23.2%	2,761,480,000	29.7%	1,161,780,000
Unaffiliated (Atheists)	1,131,150,000	16.4%	1,230,340,000	13.2%	99,190,000
Hindus	1,032,210,000	15.0%	1,384,360,000	14.9%	352,140,000
Buddhists	487,760,000	7.1%	486,270,000	5.2%	-1,490,000
Folk Religion	404,690,000	5.9%	449,140,000	4.8%	44,450,000
Other Religions	58,150,000	0.8%	61,450,000	0.7%	3,300,000
Jews	13,860,000	0.2%	16,090,000	0.2%	2,230,000
World Total	6,895,850,000	100.0%	9,307,190,000	100.0%	2,411,340,000

2010 to 2050 Number of Converts and Converts to Different Religions

	Switching in	Switching Out	Net Change	
Unaffiliated(Atheists)	97,080,000	35,590,000		+61,490,000
Muslims	12,620,000	9,400,000		+3,220,000
Folk Religions	5,460,000	2,850,000		+2,610,000
Other Religions	3,040,000	1,160,000		+1,880,000
Hindus	260,000	250,000		+10,000
Jews	320,000	630,000	-310,000	
Buddhists	3,370,000	6,210,000	-2,850,000	
Christians	40,060,000	106,110,000	-66,050,000	

Atheism currently accounts for 16.4% of the world and is one of the fastest growing religions with the largest number of adherents of any religion.

Buddhism and Jainism initially strongly opposed caste, as a result of which a large number of people began to accept these religions. But these religions did not have clear statements about God and belief in the afterlife. It was the preaching of ethics and monasticism. Instead of theoretical tendencies for the reformation of society, it was a practical philosophy, which was related to the social life of man. They were trying to achieve.

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Types of Atheism

There are three types of atheism in modern times.

1. Gnosticism

Gnosticism means to have knowledge or knowledge. These atheists have a serious attitude towards the denial of God. These people do not recognize the soul, gods, angels, heaven and hell and the spiritual and metaphysical issues related to religion in any way. They claim that they are well aware that there is no creator in the creation of man and the universe, but it has come into existence automatically and is governed by natural laws. are called Gnostic Atheists. Generally, when Atheists are mentioned, Atheists are referring to this group.¹⁴

2. Agnosticism

In a general sense, it means to consider God as beyond our understanding (thought, understanding) and adopt an attitude of silence in this matter. They say that whether there is a God or not, we cannot say anything about it. We should only think that "we don't know." These people are called Agnostic Atheists. People who believe in this belief. Stay away from both denial and acceptance of God.¹⁵

3. Deism

This theory insists on believing that God is only the creator of the universe. According to the convinced people of this theory, God has suspended himself by bringing the universe into existence and making the laws prescribed for it, so the system in the universe is now There is no intervention of any entity. And there is no moderator of this universe anymore. This belief is like if a person made an automatic watch and now that watch keeps running automatically.¹⁶

Reasons for the Development of Atheism

The famous philosopher Kant presented a special philosophy called "Positivism". According to him, the existence of only those things that can be observed and proven is accepted and the existence of the rest is rejected. Since the essence of Allah is not observable, for this reason it was denied. This philosophy of Kant became the main basis of the modern atheistic system. This civil war of religious scholars and scientists is creating a huge gap between religion and science. Due to this violence, religion and all its related issues have become abhorrent to the intellectual class, religion is unnecessary. They got fed up with beliefs, suicide, worship and all other limitations and started coming out.¹⁷

In the beginning Ladinism comes in the form of a critical narrative which targets the orthodoxy of a society and its traditions. All this is done in the name of progress and modernity. In the third stage, she appears before others in a dialectical manner with an aggressive and totalitarian attitude and wants to establish her grip on every aspect of life.¹⁸

Differences of Religions:

In the world of religions, two main types of belief exist equally with some differences: the existence of God and the concept of God's messengers known as Messengers, Prophets, Prophets, Arrow Thinkers, Buddhas and Avatars. The result of these two beliefs is that this universe was created by God and after creation, he did not become unrelated to this universe, but he is running the system of this universe. He has taught man to distinguish between good and bad and He placed this consciousness in his

self, which is called nature. Moreover, some practical patterns came from God according to which human beings should live their lives.¹⁹

The concept of God is found in every religion, while the source of heavenly religions is the same, why is there so much difference in their orders? The answer is that the people of these religions continued to change these orders for their own will and benefit and finally a new form of these religions emerged which was not acceptable to human reason and society. People also began to move away from religion because it was too difficult for them to live on the path of religion, like Christianity adopted monasticism when the worldly people could not. Buddhism also adopted monasticism but was forced by secularism to make changes in its religion, similarly Hinduism tried to incorporate every religion into itself and incorporated some of their beliefs into its religion. Tried to recognize the damage to his identity.

The rate of atheism is increasing in the world, but the surprising thing is that in the societies that try to impose religion by force, punishments are given for the slightest thing and fatwas of disbelief will be imposed and they will be excluded from the realm of religion. Atheism is spreading more rapidly there than in civilized societies. Atheism first invaded Europe and confined Christianity to the church and made religion a private matter. For the same reasons. Atheism flourished in Europe. After that, he turned to Islam. For this, the believers of atheism resorted to various institutions and philosophers through which they raise questions on the beliefs of Islam, religious sectarianism. Misinterpretation of something is spread on social media and an attempt is made to turn the youth away from religion by raising more questions from them.

Atheists use the bad deeds of the believers as a basis and present them as evidence. Today's atheists will have a lot of innovation in their work that was not there before, atheists of Christians, Qadiyans, Jews, Hindus and other religions. They collect the objections and publicize them through the Internet social media. By spreading these ideas, the atheists benefit a lot. College and university students who are already away from religion, they fall into delusion.²⁰

Another religious reason for the spread of Al-Aid is the widening gap between religious scholars in the name of sects, there are thousands of different religious interpretations on which even they themselves have not been able to agree to this day. It has completely failed to co-ordinate; everyone is busy playing their own beans and saving their own sects. But remember that the angles of thinking are changing day by day and you are still with the medieval mentality. Want to move on.²¹

No religion has been immune from the influence of atheism. So it needs to remove all religious differences and eliminate sectarianism and create harmony to prevent atheism.

Lack of satisfactory answers:

When the distorted Christianity was presented by the European Church, it did not satisfy the reason. When people put it against the reason, it became difficult for them to accept the religion and they started raising different questions. Religious people did not have the answer. When atheism started spreading and questions about religion started being raised, they resorted to repression to stop it and various punishments were given to atheists and those who hold such ideas. Temporarily this movement will be suppressed but it could not end when this movement got the opportunity, it changed Christianity in Europe and limited it to the churches.²²

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The young generation, which is away from religion, is created on the basis of new ideas, objections, philosophical, intellectual, historical, weak and subjective traditions and expressions. Atheists encourage them to question these doubts. When they do not get satisfactory answers to these questions, they turn to atheism.

Humanism and Teaching Ethics:

Any philosophy or life system is first created by the most intelligent people of the society and then spread it through their speech and writing to the intelligent class of the society, which is commonly called the elite. It controls the means. After accepting this philosophy or system of life, it conveys it to the common people. The people are subject to this elite in every matter, so they accept it wholeheartedly. People of the West. The intelligent people who participated in the promotion of atheistic ideas were not morally depraved people. They presented themselves as the bearers of human ethics. And they consider themselves champions of morality.²³

Paul Kurtz, founder of the Council for Secular Humanism, writes in his *The war we have to fight on the third side is the war of human morality. We believe that the moral revolution is the only guarantee for the future of humanity. This is what makes human life better without the belief of salvation in the hereafter or heaven. We want to test moral values based on observation and argument and be prepared to change our moral values in the light of the results. is universal, as emphasized in the Humanist Manifesto 2000. We believe that every human being on this planet Earth is absolutely equal. Our commitment to ethics is to ensure that every individual in the world has his or her rights and to protect our common home, the earth. Human ethics guarantees individual freedom, right to privacy, human freedom and social justice. It is related to the welfare of the entire human race.*²⁴

Education System:

Curriculum plays a very important role in the development of any country. The role of a curriculum is to enable the student to acquire knowledge, develop ideas and abilities, guide a complete change in the personality in terms of attitudes, values and habits. , plays a role proportional to the cultural, economic, moral facts.²⁵

Separation of modern sciences and religious studies is also a reason for spreading atheism because the curriculum of modern sciences is also compiled by people who are themselves victims of atheism. The imprint of the sciences is seen on which the ideas of European authors are taught to our students, due to which they are first away from religion and then they are attracted towards atheism.

Atheists also influenced the education system. The education system, which was previously dominated by religion, was brought under the modern system in which there was no place for religion. According to the Oxford Dictionary:

"Of education instruction relating to non-religion subjects."²⁶

The education system plays an important role in showing a new way to any society; therefore, atheists start interfering in the education system of any society before targeting it. With its help, the new generation is slowly being made intelligent. And they are away from religion.

First, in Europe, religion was separated from the education system by declaring it a personal issue, and now the same formula is being tried in the East.

Science and the Modern Age:

Atheists of ancient times did not have a solid logical argument for atheism. In the nineteenth century, some scientific theories emerged that supported atheism to some extent.

Medieval Christian scholars incorporated into their belief systems some of the canonical and philosophical ideas of their time, such as the earth being the center of the universe and the sun revolving around it. When these ideas were disproved by modern scientific research, many people lost faith in Christianity as a whole and adopted atheism intellectually. The doubts raised by these atheists about the nature of God were based on some scientific theories.

The period of the nineteenth century and the first half of the twentieth century is the period of the rise of atheism. In this period, the scientific researches that brought attention to the atheistic ideas took place. In the same period, atheistic ideas and life systems were promoted all over the world. Over time, people all over the world accepted atheism at different levels in their lives. Some accepted atheism theoretically and became pure, atheistic and duplicitous, and some only accepted its practical effects.

Man is progressing day by day and has conquered the moon and the earth. New inventions are reducing religious love. History is witnessing that religion has opposed science and punished its followers. With its help worldly facilities were made possible to change people's thinking.²⁷

Blind imitation:

In physics, inventions, historical discoveries and modern researches, the West has the leadership of the whole world today. When a nation reaches this point, the world starts adopting its every effort. And the thought is becoming engrossing. If they return to the horrors of the past, they rebelled against all the restrictions of religion and society, they raised the social system by chanting the slogan of sexual freedom, then millions of imitators will be born in the East, who are two or four times eviler than them. There will be steps ahead.²⁸

Economic System:

Atheist thought introduced new systems to the world so that its ideas could spread in every era and every society, so atheism gave the world two systems. One of them is Adam Smith's capitalist system or capitalism and the other is Karl Marx's. Communism or Kahanism.

Capitalism is actually a form of feudalism that is little better than feudalism in practice. Capitalism leaves the market completely free in which everyone is free to spend as much wealth as they want. A person who has unlimited opportunities to earn wealth will become richer from rich and if these opportunities are not available, he will become poorer from poor, the government does not interfere in this regard.²⁹

In Europe, Karl Marx started a great movement against the exploitation of capitalism, in which he criticized the economic injustices of this system. In which he declared economy as the center of human life and human history. According to him, all the wars of history, all religions and all political systems are the product of economics. He believed in God, Prophethood and the hereafter. By denying it, he presented a new system to the world, which will be remembered in history as communism. The system of communism was a purely atheistic system.

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Regarding the economic system, the atheists are divided into two groups. One group is convinced of the capitalist system, which is based on profit, while the other is convinced of communism. The capitalist system insists that man should have complete freedom of commercial and industrial activities. It should be left that he should adopt whatever method he deems appropriate to earn profit, there should be no distinction between halal and haram under religious laws for obtaining profit. Also, interest, insurance, interest, etc. are of primary importance in this economic system. Got it. On the contrary, in the co-operative system, any business is not a personal property of a person but a national property and all individuals are employed by the government. Different forms of co-operatives are prevalent in the present day.³⁰

Materialism:

Materialism is a process due to which man is not only distant from man, but also distant from religion. In his greed and pursuit of material (wealth) he becomes so blinded that he does not distinguish between right and wrong. People who are rich or powerful use such methods to protect their wealth. Thanks to which their wealth is protected and increased, while they spend their wealth to subdue their opponents. Religion because it advises to work for the good of humanity, illegal hoarding, illegal profits. etc. therefore, religion is the biggest enemy for materialists. Therefore, they resorted to atheism to destroy religion and supported and financed it in every forum. So that atheism can spread.

The system that is in force in the world at the moment is the capitalist system. This system worships materialism. In this system, wealth can be collected in any way, there is no limitation of halal and haram. Such thought and concern has been provided by secularism. Because as long as economics was under the shadow of religious teachings, the element of halal and haram remained in it in one form or another.³¹

Materialism has also played an important role in strengthening atheism. The capitalist system is its main link. The capitalist is more concerned about his capital than anything else, and he uses legitimate and illegitimate methods to protect it. While religion does not allow it to do these things. For this reason, the capitalist system tried to promote atheism in comparison to religion and created various institutions for it, which they called NGOs, NGOs. Gaya, which apparently works for human welfare but behind the scenes is trying to spread atheistic ideas.

Political System:

Atheism used secularism as a political weapon. In the modern era, Western thinkers presented the theory that religion has no role in state affairs, that is, religion has no part in the modern political system, for example, Shams Kanwal writes in this context. "Secularism favors keeping religion at a distance from the state and politics, but in a secular society every citizen has full freedom to practice his religious beliefs in his private life."³²

Dr. Anwar Pasha writes, "In the modern era, the scope of politics on the basis of religion has ended, and in the modern era, wherever politics has been tried on the basis of religion, there have been no happy results. Government and politics have also been tried on the basis of religion. Neither the sanctity of religion could remain there nor the credibility of politics. "Politics is the bond of religion."³³

Atheists began to control its political system to control the country and ended the patronage of religion in its name so that religion would not interfere with the laws of the country and the opportunity for atheists to play openly found.

Social Media:

Today's era is called the era of social media which is playing an important role in making the young generation intelligent. Atheists are making ample use of it to confuse their teachings and attack their opponents. If it is said that the biggest weapon of atheists in today's era is social media, then it will not be out of place. Through print, electronic and social media, doubts and doubts have been systematically attacked against all religions, atheists deny the existence of Allah, the concept of Prophethood, the belief in the Hereafter, the Book of Allah and the historical status of the Prophets. They seem to be trying to confuse minds with questions, The religions which were already suffering from contradictions and standing on weak foundations in these beliefs and problems could not stay long in front of their philosophical and spiritual invasion and atheism easily took root in their societies. Atheists have taken advantage of the internet and will form groups on various websites and social media to spread propaganda together and preach atheism to the new generation.

Freedom of expression:

One of the reasons for the spread of atheism is freedom of expression and this freedom is an attempt to get it in the name of rights, which includes freedom from religious practices, restrictions, in short mother-father freedom, because they do not tolerate any kind of interference in their personal affairs. Due to which all the youth are being drawn towards it.

In the name of rights and freedom of expression, the right to vote, atheists have raised a storm of abuse. Questions are raised based on the personal life and religious beliefs of religious leaders.

One of the reasons for spreading atheism is sexual freedom. According to most atheists, the fulfillment of sexual desires like food, drink and sleep is a natural desire of man, so he should be allowed to fulfill his sexual desire as he wants. It is wrong, but there is nothing wrong with consensual sex. The concept of free sex was first proposed by Sigmund Freud, a well-known atheist psychologist and neurologist in the West. If desires like hunger, thirst, etc. are not fulfilled, then one becomes a victim of diseases, similarly, if sexual desire is not fulfilled, a person becomes sick.³⁴

Role of NGOs:

These are organizations that are spreading atheism in the name of human welfare. In this regard, they resort to slogans like freedom of expression, human rights, personal freedom, and restoration rights. They show that their work is to propagate against religion in the veil. For this, multinational companies and atheist organizations provide funding in the name of welfare.

Results:

There have always been people in human societies who denied religion and God, but a movement of atheism has been born out of the amazing material development and scientific inventions of the present age. Atheism is the denial of all religions on earth. The name of religion, religion, God and the absolute denial of a supreme being is called atheism. According to atheists, the world called metaphysics is an illusion. The universe is only the name of existence and perception. There is no such thing as an intangible, invisible metaphysical and spiritual world. These are all human superstitions and ideas. According to a conservative estimate, atheism is the most popular ideology in the world today, because of which thousands of people are converted to it every day. They have

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been denying God and religion or raising various questions. The invention of the Internet and social media has turned the temptation of atheism into an organized movement is targeted.

The biggest target of today's atheists on the net is the religion of Islam. The main reason is that Islam has given man a complete system of life. A Muslim needs it in every moment of life, while the religion of Islam is in places of worship. Among all the religions of the world, Islam is the only religion that stands like a leaden wall in front of atheism. Islam offers a comprehensive and perfect solution to all the problems of humanity. The direction of cannons is towards Islam. In this regard, their easy target is the young generation who are far from Islam. Doubts and doubts are created in their hearts by basing the subject traditions and phrases on the weak and subject of history and traditions.

Answers to the questions of the youth and their objections should be removed in a scientific and research way. If you want to evaluate the work of the atheists, look at their website, forum, on the Internet. Can be guessed.

The temptation of atheism has risen like a storm in the present age. All religions are under attack. The atheists are attacking these religions from all sides. What are the reasons due to which atheism is spreading so fast? If we find these reasons and prevent them, we can to some extent stop these storms.

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